

FORMS AND METHODS OF ORGANIZING TECHNOLOGY LESSONS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Labor education certainly plays a special role in the education of a perfect personality. Technology and training will serve educational purposes, such as types of mental and physical work, developing a broad understanding of employment processes, as well as developing one's skills in the world of work.*

The purpose of technological education and training at school: to instill in students a love of work and respect for working people; introduce students to the basics and technological processes of modern industrial and agricultural production, construction, transport and services; to develop their labor skills and abilities in the process of study and socially useful work; is to encourage informed choice of profession and obtaining initial vocational education.

Keywords: *education, upbringing and training, labor education, goals and objectives of technological education, technological education and society, methodological teaching system, forms and types of training, elements of elementary technology.*

The tasks of technological science and vocational training are solved in primary school with the help of the entire educational system and all educational subjects. This, in turn, sets important goals and tasks for the science of technology and its teaching methodology taught in the higher education system.

In the 4th grade Technology textbook of I.A.Mannopova, R.A.Mavlonova, N.R.Ibragimova general secondary schools, the word technology is defined as follows: "Technology" (Greek, teche-skill, art, logos-teaching) the science of ways of processing raw materials and materials with the help of production tools. In particular, the main goal of teaching this subject is to familiarize students with the content and tasks of technology, teaching methods, and educational tools in elementary grades and to apply them theoretically and practically in the process of teaching technology in lessons and outside the classroom. is the formation of knowledge, skills and competences.

In addition, teaching young people to value work and professions, explaining their importance in social life, creating knowledge about the basics (technology) of professions, and forming professional training in children from school age are the main tasks of labor education teachers. It is known that the main goals and tasks of technology science in elementary grades are: moral and psychological preparation for work, equipping students with basic polytechnic knowledge, practical training in technology science, equipping students with the skills and abilities of technological operations, in the process of technological science consists of comprehensive cultivation. Therefore, the science of technology and its teaching methodology includes: providing all-round theoretical and practical knowledge to future teachers, improving the consistency of providing information about professions in the primary classes of general education schools, the requirements of the State Education Standards includes the tasks of imparting theoretical and practical knowledge.

The science of technology and its teaching methods is considered a subject of the educational methods course, based on the results of the main scientific researches of the science, enriched with advanced pedagogical experiences and based on materials based on modern technologies. Preparing students for practical technological processes and ensuring that they acquire the skills and abilities of basic technological operations. The educational value of technology is also important. It forms students' understanding of types of work, creates interest in work, and plays an important role in educating hard work, responsibility, discipline, sense of duty and sense of community. It also creates a foundation for students to develop intellectually. It helps in the development of will and moral qualities.

The formation of a feeling for work in students will educate them such qualities as friendship, brotherhood, helping each other, community, respect. The science of technology and its teaching methodology requires the proper use of modern information and pedagogical technologies to carry out educational and educational work. In order for students to diligently master the science of technology, textbooks, instructional manuals, and technical tools should be used at school.

Particular attention should be paid to the use of modern information technologies, the use of interactive methods, the implementation of educational tools and educational games in the educational process. We will discuss these in more detail in the following topics. In every lesson, it is very important to expand and strengthen the scope of knowledge and skills of students, to create stable positive skills and habits in them, and to educate them ethically for work. That is, it is necessary not to make the task of the lesson only to impart knowledge and create skills, but also to connect it with the tasks of intellectual education and perfection. That's why the teacher, while preparing for a topic, should clearly imagine what ideas of morality will lead students to understand, develop attention, thinking, memory, imagination, will, and among other things, how to achieve the perfection of personal qualities based on this lesson material. It is necessary.

In accordance with the content of the science of technology, students acquire practical skills and abilities to use simple tools and devices used in processing materials that are convenient for this age group. Simple tools are the main basis of special tools and machines. Equipping with practical skills and knowledge also means teaching basic production operations. The technology of objects encountered by elementary school students is diverse, but it is not difficult to perceive the typicality of work operations without studying this issue in detail, which are: measuring and marking of material; bending and shearing them; joining and strengthening parts by gluing, sewing, braiding and tying; collecting details and assembling the product. The final operation is to decorate the item. The formation of graphic skills is also related to the practical preparation of primary school students for work.

It is very important to identify students' inclination and interest in a certain type of technology and help them to improve their work skills in their favorite classes. Experience shows that only if children have a good idea of the structure of the whole object, they can learn the type, shape, size and other characteristics of the work, as well as the methods of working with labor tools faster and more thoroughly. Especially 1st grade students try to imitate the teacher. For this reason, the teacher should be able to mentally approach the students to each type of work and mentally prepare them to perform the assigned task. Labor qualifications and skills play a big role in teaching and educating students about technology science and preparing them for future practical activities. One of the tasks of teaching technology science to lower grade students is to form a number of work skills and abilities in them.

It is not only a result of labor qualifications and skills, but also a condition for attracting students to work, socially useful production work. There is a great opportunity to practice the ability to observe in the practical preparation of junior high school students for technology science. These are observation of its changes in the process of material processing, observation of the working characteristics of various tools in different production and work situations, and practical determination of the expediency of labor operations. By observing their own work and that of their peers, students compare, compare, and evaluate design solutions, finishing methods and quality of finished products and their details. Indicators such as auxiliary and processing operations, simple, convenient and easy work methods, the amount of time spent on work will not be overlooked by the students. All these together require active thinking activity and help students' mental development.

Observations and the simplest experiments performed by elementary school students in technology classes are based on the simultaneous use of all analyzers, in particular, the movement apparatus of each student. It is the characteristics and quality of various materials (soft-hard; light-heavy; dense-porous; strong-thin; clear, white, colored, etc.) and also allows to give more accurate and correct answers to the questions about the resistance properties of each material during processing.

The use of various types of work activities in technology classes is an important basis of the knowledge and skills of the students in the field of technological operations. An important result of students' activity in technology classes is their independent identification of new signs and characteristics of objects and phenomena being studied, drawing conclusions that become more precise and systematic from lesson to lesson. For example, in one of the lessons, the teacher sets the students the task of identifying the types of paper, describing the general properties of paper as a material with many functions, and the unlimited possibilities of its application and use. Students gradually learn to distinguish these properties, to look for and find properties similar to other materials, and to justify their selection for specific practical purposes. All of these are important for children to develop the skills of designing and making things correctly.

Technology lessons are organized in several forms. In particular, graphic works occupy an important place in teaching technical work. A whole lesson, sometimes two lessons, is devoted to drawing something. Therefore, before starting to draw a drawing in technical technology classes, it is necessary to familiarize students with the elements necessary for making drawings based on the program. Practical work helps students learn to apply their acquired knowledge in practice. It is of great educational and educational importance for students to independently draw up a plan for carrying out practical work. The performance of visual aids by students can also be included in practical work, which helps to strengthen the acquired knowledge. Laboratory work can be at different stages of education. Conducting laboratory work increases the credibility of acquired knowledge, helps to consolidate knowledge, and serves to teach how to apply it in practice. Laboratory work can also be conducted for the purpose of imparting new knowledge. In this process, students develop a sense of responsibility, observation, and attentiveness.

Independent work is work that is done without the direct participation of the teacher, but at a specially allocated time by his assignment. In this place, students apply their aspirations and express the results of their mental and physical actions in one form or another and consciously try to achieve the goal set in the task. In the process of independent work, along with the formation of skills, students test their strength, knowledge and abilities.

Excursions play an important role in increasing interest in learning, instilling independence skills in students and learning about life. It will be more effective if production representatives also participate in conducting tours. During the excursion, students will get to know the production technology. Before the excursion, clear goals are set before the students, and after the excursion there will be a question and answer session. Formation of attitude to work. This process is one of the important aspects of technological science. The task of developing children's memories plays an important role in forming an attitude to work and making training more successful. Because memorizing educational materials in technology classes has its own characteristics compared to other subjects. Elementary school students should be able to understand the names of all new tools, materials, operations, and objects by sight and hearing. For this, the teacher should not only explain in the labor class, but also show the sample of materials and items, tools, methods of material processing, consistency of operations.

In order for the student to have a stable attitude to work, he should know the content of the education, listen and see the information diligently. New knowledge and skills are embodied in the minds of students from the labor lesson to the next labor lesson, encourages them to expand the scope of their memories, and further increases the relationship to the types of work.

Emotional processes are also characteristic in the formation of attitude to work. It is necessary to teach children to overcome difficulties, to enter the path of achieving the set goal with perseverance and determination, not to abandon the work started, but to finish it. In this place, it is very important to show positive emotions: joy, pleasure and satisfaction from work.

At work, various psychological states are manifested: activity, concentration, interest, independent thinking, feelings of dissatisfaction. The main tasks of technology education and training in primary schools are to prepare students for work, teaching and improving the consistency of the choice of profession in the primary classes of general education schools, educating students according to the requirements of state education standards, and preparing students for the profession - consists of providing theoretical and practical knowledge to become a craftsman.

In order to create a culture of work, children's attention should always be drawn to the rules and arrangement of tools and materials, proper equipment of the workplace, methods of economical use of materials, standards and quality of work, activities that ensure performance, it is necessary to insist on the accuracy and cleanliness obtained in processing and finally to decorate the thing beautifully. The main tasks of technology education are determined by the goals and tasks of education, and it is moral and psychological preparation for work, equipping students with basic technical knowledge, practical training for work, equipping students with work qualifications and skills, training students for work. It consists of all-round cultivation in the process of cultivation. We will study these tasks separately in the following topics.

Attitude to work, understanding the importance and necessity of this work, showing zeal in such work, approaching work with a sense of personal responsibility means economical attitude to social property.

Ethical training for work consists in teaching children to work in a team, friendly mutual support, creative initiative, organizational skills and teaching norms of behavior at work.

Mental preparation for work is a complex, long-lasting and multifaceted process, which is absorbed into the entire labor education and training. Although it has its own characteristics, it is very close to moral preparation for work. Mentally preparing a child for work means forming a

conscious and positive attitude towards work in accordance with his age, forming an interest in acquiring practical skills and abilities.

The task of the teacher is to help the students to understand that work is the conscience and duty of everyone, that a person is honored by his work, that the best qualities of a person can develop and improve only in the work done for the welfare of the Motherland. Children's ability to work is very important for everyone to understand the need to participate in the production of tools necessary for the life and activity of society, its well-being. Also, children should learn that a person cannot live in society without work.

Mental preparation for work involves the development and improvement of various psychological processes. These are perception, emotional perception, attention, memory, thinking and similar processes. In other words, they are called psychological components of labor. When training for work, it is necessary to improve the process of emotional cognition, taking into account the child's capabilities. It is known that labor activity and labor education are characterized by the combination of various senses (sight, hearing, touch, taste, skin, muscle movement). Therefore, when teachers introduce a new material or tool to students of the lower grades, they activate all types of children's senses: children grab the paper, stroke it, turn it over and examine it, listen to how it rustles. Such activation of senses not only helps to get a more complete picture of information, but also develops and improves this psychological process.

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